

Understanding Work Stress in Public Organizations: A Study of Team Conflict and the Mediating Role of Service Climate

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Abstract— This study examines the patterns of work-related stress in public organisations, specifically investigating how team conflict affects employees and how service climate plays a role in moderating this influence. The study utilises a sample of 656 participants selected from an original pool of 800. The data is analysed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The results demonstrate a notable association between team conflict and work stress, emphasising the harmful impact of internal conflicts on the well-being of employees. Furthermore, the study demonstrates that service climate has a substantial impact on occupational stress, indicating that a service atmosphere that provides assistance might help reduce stress levels. Service climate is an important factor that mediates the relationship between team conflict and work stress. This highlights the crucial role it plays in public organisations. These observations enhance our comprehension of how the internal workings of an organisation impact employee stress and emphasise the need of cultivating a favourable service environment to mitigate the negative consequences of team discord.

Keywords— *Work stress, team conflict, service climate, public organization*

I. INTRODUCTION

In public administration, employee stress significantly impacts service quality. Team conflict, stemming from diverse perspectives and work styles, is a major stressor affecting job satisfaction, engagement, and productivity [1]. This study examines how team conflict contributes to work stress and how service climate mediates this effect in public organizations. Service climate, which fosters high-quality service, might mitigate team conflict's effects, enhancing employee well-being and service outcomes. Team conflict includes task-related and relationship-related conflicts, both leading to stress and potential health issues [2]. Chronic stress can lead to pathological behaviours and physical symptoms [3]. Poor team interactions can cause stress [4], while a positive service climate can improve employee commitment and reduce stress [5]. Employees in supportive environments are better equipped to handle job challenges [6]. This article provides empirical insights for improving work conditions and service quality.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

A. The Work Stress

Stress, as [7] have noted, frequently arises when individuals encounter threat for which they lack a solution or effective coping mechanism. Uncontrolled stress can become even more perilous. [8] point out that work-related stress has detrimental effects on task efficiency and job satisfaction, which, in turn, indirectly contributes to absenteeism. As delineated by [9], work stress is a consequence of the interplay between an employee's personality and their job conditions, particularly when team conflict and service climate exceed what the employee can handle [10]. Optimal work performance occurs when an individual's need and available resources are in equilibrium, while stress emerges when there is an indication that these two aspects are not aligned. Work stress, a persistent problem that impacts employee performance, triggers emotional, psychological, and physiological responses. Work stress, due to its high occurrence, has a detrimental effect on both organisations and employees [11].

1) Service Climate and Work Stress:

According to [12], service climate is how workers think about the actions and habits that are supported, encouraged, and expected when dealing with customers. Organisational climate, or service climate, is how people feel about the things in their environment that affect their expectations for outcomes, needs, contingencies, and interactions at work [13]. Service climate is a specific part of organisational climate. This idea of organisational climate is based on the idea that workers determine their work environment by combining the small things they see every day at work with bigger ideas they have about the bigger themes that run through their workplace [14]. Thus, when an organisation prioritises the delivery of

exceptional service, it creates a favourable service atmosphere within the organisation [15]. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: The Service Climate positively impacts Work Stress.

2) *Team Conflict and Work Stress:*

According to [16], work teams are defined by their collective performance surpassing individual contributions. [17] notes that teamwork has become a major focus in social psychology and organizational studies, with many tasks today relying on collaborative efforts. Although teamwork can foster innovation and performance, it can also introduce stress, leading to conflicts, over-dependence, and unequal recognition [18]. Prompt conflict resolution is crucial for a positive work environment, as minor disputes can escalate if ignored. [19] supports this, highlighting that workplace conflicts are common and can lead to various issues within teams. The following hypothesis is examined:

H2: Team conflict positively impacts work stress

3) *Mediating Effect of Service Climate:*

Service climate is a distinct component of organisational climate. It refers to the overall perceptions that individuals have about the works factors that influence their expectations, responsibilities, and interactions in a work setting [13]. The concept of organisational climate is based on the idea that employees combine their daily observations of workplace events with broader perceptions of the overall themes in their work environment [14]. Therefore, when an organisation prioritises providing exceptional service, it creates a favourable service atmosphere within the organisation [15]. Research by [6] indicates that a positive service climate helps employees feel connected to the organisation, which in turn increases their participation at work and mitigates the negative effects of stress. According to [20], employees are better equipped to handle job challenges, alleviate role stress, and avoid exhaustion when they perceive a positive organisational service atmosphere.

In a study conducted by [21], it was discovered that the organisational climate significantly influences the inclination to quit, and this influence is intensified by increased levels of stress.

H3: Service Climate mediates the relationship between team conflict and Work Stress

III.METHODOLOGY

This study examines the impact of work stress (WS) on public organizations and contributing factors using hypothesis testing. A survey was distributed to government employees, with 702 responses collected from 800 questionnaires. After excluding 46 incomplete replies, 656 responses from middle and lower management were used. Participants rated three criteria (TC, SC, and WS) on a five-point Likert scale. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM). The sample size met the requirement of 84 participants for 80% power and medium effect size, with 656 responses sufficient for the analysis.

A. Respondents' Demographics

The age breakdown among the survey participants was as follows: The age distribution of the population is as follows: 5.9% were between the ages of 21 and 25, 15.4% were between the ages of 26 and 30, 23.8% were between the ages of 36 and 40, 32.3% were between the ages of 41 and 45, 5.5% were between the ages of 46 and 50, and 3.4% were between the ages of 51 and 60. Regarding the highest degree of education, the respondents exhibited a range of differences. 3.5% of the individuals had a Master's degree, 29% had a Bachelor's degree, 34.0% had a Diploma, 3.7% possessed a Certificate, 7.9% had a Malaysian Higher Certificate of Education (STPM), 20.9% had a Malaysian Certificate of Education (SPM), and 0.6% had a Lower Secondary Assessment (PMR). In terms of job experience, a mere 8.4% of the participants had more than 21 years of experience in their respective fields. Additionally, 19.2% had between 16 and 20 years of experience, 34.3% had between 11 and 15 years of experience, and the majority, 38.1%, had between 5 and 10 years of experience.

B. Descriptive Statistics

Table I displays the statistical data for the variable, including the average values, standard deviations (SDs), and correlations. Significantly, both the TC and SC variables exhibited a noteworthy correlation with WS.

TABLE I
MEANS, SDs, AND CORRELATIONS

	Mean	SD	TC	SC	WS
TC	18.33	6.63	-		
SC	27.07	3.70	-0.205**	-	
WS	63.09	20.84	0.372**	0.366**	-

**p<0.01

TC: Team Conflict, SC: Service Climate, WS: Work stress

C. Measurement Model

Before assessing the discriminant validity of a model, it is essential to first evaluate its convergent validity, as recommended by [22]. Once the measurement model had been established, the structural model was applied to test the research hypotheses.

1) Convergent Validity:

Prior to assessing discriminant validity, it is essential to analyse convergent validity to verify the suitability of a model, as highlighted by [22]. Once the measuring model was established, the research hypotheses were examined using the structural model. The research conducted by [23] suggests examining factor loadings, average variance extracted (AVE), and composite reliability (CR) to determine convergent validity.

The analysis results shown that most factor loadings surpassed the threshold of 0.7, with only a few falling within the range of 0.4 to 0.7. The average variance extracted (AVE) was greater than 0.5, indicating excellent convergent validity of the constructs. Additionally, all composite reliability (CR) values were higher than 0.7, further confirming the strong convergent validity of the constructs, as suggested by [24].

2) Discriminant Validity:

In accordance with the methodology described by [25], the evaluation of discriminant validity consisted of identifying indicators that solely represented a single component within the dataset. In order to establish that these components are statistically different from other variables, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive assessment of discriminant validity, as emphasised by [23]. Thus, the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) was utilised, following the suggestion of [26], who stated that the HTMT threshold should be less than 0.90 to confirm discriminant validity. As shown in Table II, the findings substantiated the existence of discriminant validity.

TABLE III
DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY (HTMT) RATIO

	TC	SC	WS
TC			
SC	0.224		
WS	0.386	0.398	

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Hypothesis Testing

The findings indicated a favourable and statistically significant influence of service climate on work stress ($\beta = -0.313$, $t = 8.643$; lower limit [LL] = -0.380, upper limit [UL] = -0.238, $p < 0.05$), hence confirming the hypothesis H1. Furthermore, there was a significant positive relationship between team conflict and work stress ($\beta = 0.309$, $t = 8.136$; LL = 0.229, UL = 0.378, $p < 0.05$), providing support for hypothesis H2. The study examined the role of service climate as a mediator in the connection between team conflict and work stress. To address potential bias, a 95% confidence interval was established using 5,000 bootstrap samples. The study confirmed hypothesis H3 by demonstrating that service climate plays a major mediating role in the link between TC and WS. The mediation effect was shown to be statistically significant ($\beta = 0.066$, $t = 4.416$; LL = 0.039, UL = 0.097, $p < 0.05$). Table III offers a comprehensive summary of the empirical evidence, demonstrating a clear and direct correlation, while Table IV presents the results of the mediation analysis.

TABLE III
HYPOTHESIS TESTING (DIRECT EFFECT)

Hypothesis		B	SE	t	p	LL	UL	Decision	VIF
H1	SC -> WS	-0.313	0.036	8.643	0.000	-0.380	-0.238	Supported	1.046
H2	TC-> WS	0.309	0.038	8.136	0.000	0.229	0.378	Supported	1.046

** $p \leq 0.05$. SE, standard error.

SC: Service climate, TC: Team Conflict, WS; Work Stress

TABLE IV
MEDIATING EFFECT

Hypothesis		B	SE	t	p	LL	UL	Result
H3	TC -> SC -> WS	0.066	0.015	4.416	0.000	0.039	0.097	Supported

** $p \leq 0.05$. SE, standard error.

SC: Service climate, TC: Team Conflict, WS; Work Stress

B. Coefficient of Significance (R^2), Predictive relevance (Q^2), and Effect size (f^2)

Table V provides R^2 , f^2 , and Q^2 value as predictor of work stress and service climate. The results indicate that team conflict and service climate together explained 23.4% of the total variation in work stress, as reflected an R^2 value of 0.234. Additionally, team conflict accounted for 4.4% of the overall variance in SC, as indicated by an R^2 value of 0.044. [27] categorized an R^2 value of 23.4% in this study as moderate.

In addition, the predicted accuracy study utilised [28] Q^2 . A blindfolded approach was employed to evaluate the model's ability to make accurate predictions. The Q^2 value represents the level of importance of the prediction for the criteria variable. It is considered significant when the Q^2 score is more than 0, with a threshold distance of seven [29]. Within this particular context, the criteria variables WS and SC displayed Q^2 values of 0.134 and 0.025, respectively, indicating a reasonable level of predictive significance. [30] categorised f^2 values of 0.35, 0.15, and 0.02 as being large, medium, and small effects, respectively. Regarding the impact of service climate and team conflict variables on work stress, both factors had a minor effect, as evidenced by a f^2 value of 0.122 and 0.119, respectively.

TABLE V
THE R^2 , Q^2 , AND f^2

	R^2	Q^2	f^2	Decision
WS	0.234	0.134		
SC	0.044	0.025	0.122 ^a	Small
TC			0.119 ^a	Small

^aWS

SC: Service climate, TC: Team Conflict, WS; Work Stress

Prior studies on government employees have identified various work stressors that significantly influence their work stress. This study aims to examine the factors contributing to work stress and the relationship between these stressors among federal public sector employees in Malaysia, particularly those in Putrajaya. The lack of data on the connections between work stresses and stress among public officials prompted this research. It explores the relationships between service climate, team conflict, and work stress among Malaysian federal government employees.

The primary aim is to examine the associations between service climate and work stress. Hypothesis 1 (H1) posits that service climate positively affects Malaysian civil servants' work stress, indicating that service climate characteristics influence employee well-being and stress levels. This aligns with previous research showing a positive relation between public service motivation and stress [31]. Public organisations must assess and manage service climate to mitigate work stress [32].

The second objective is to examine how team conflict influences work stress among Malaysian federal public sector employees. Hypothesis 2 (H2) states that team conflict affects workplace stress. Bootstrapping analysis shows a positive correlation between team conflict and occupational stress, supported by earlier studies [33]. Factors such as harsh treatment, lack of cooperation, and negative emotional confrontations contribute to stress [4]. These assumptions are bolstered by previous studies that asserted that stressful team conflicts in the workplace can be characterised by a lack of support or encouragement from teammates, as well as by interpersonal disagreements, negative emotional confrontations, and broken communication [34].

The third objective is to determine the mediation effect of service climate on the relationship between team conflict and work stress. Hypothesis 3 (H3) states that service climate mediates this relationship. Bootstrapping analysis confirms that service climate significantly affects the team conflict-work stress relationship, showing that a positive service climate can mitigate the negative impacts of role stress. This is consistent with [35] who state that service climate represents how incumbents understand messages provided through HR practices or top management about expected and rewarded behaviours, which promote desirable less stress. This study suggests that organisational service climate research is important. Service climate is essential to implementing organisational resources and management concepts [36]. Effective management methods must be integrated into human resource procedures due to the substantial association between service climate and work stress. Personality tests in recruiting and selection reduce stress and boost job satisfaction by aligning people with their responsibilities. In conclusion, the study confirmed the need to consistently improve methods. Organisations can change and correct to strengthen their vulnerabilities.

V. CONCLUSION

This study examines workplace stress among civil servants in Putrajaya, Malaysia's administrative centre, focusing on job-related and social-organizational factors leading to poor service climate and team conflict. Establishing ground rules within teams is crucial to manage diverse interactions, preventing misunderstandings and conflicts. Key guidelines include honesty, respect, tolerance, unity, and support. Effective management practices and personality tests in HR can align individuals with their roles, reducing stress and enhancing job satisfaction. The study emphasizes the importance of continuous improvement in organizational methods to address vulnerabilities and maintain a positive service climate.

This study reveals insights into service climate, team conflict, and work stress in public organizations. Limitations include the inability to establish causality due to a cross-sectional design and potential common method bias. Future research should employ longitudinal or experimental designs and incorporate multi-source and objective measurements for better validity and reliability.

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